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Welcome to our first newsletter! We plan to release these newsletters regularly to keep our alumni up to date with what's happening with the schools. It's been a busy year for the schools as we continue to expand despite the constraints.

In this newsletter we bring you reports from our latest schools including our first virtual summer school, hosted by ICTP in Trieste along with reports on the physical schools that we also ran.

We are very pleased to tell you that the Data Schools have a new website - datascienceschools.org - which we invite you to visit, particularly as we are launching our alumni network here. More on this soon!

San José December 2019

CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School (#dataSanJosé19) took place during December 2-13, 2019 at the Centro Nacional de Alta Tecnología (CeNAT), in San José, Costa Rica. It was the first School in Central America and it was held completely in English. The majority of the attendants were from Costa Rica (85%), but we also had participants from six other countries: Brazil, Peru, Colombia, Nicaragua, Belize and Dominican Republic. The two week event consisted of daily work from 9am to 5pm, with classes where group work was encouraged. From the 32 registered participants, 44% were female and 54% were full time students (14 Masters and 3 PhD). Other participants were junior faculty and researchers in areas such as meteorology, statistics, biology, hydrology, civil engineering, computer science, among others, from major universities in their countries. The event was possible thanks to the effort of a team of about 15 people including directors, hosts, instructors and helpers.

Besides the CODATA-RDA Schools sponsors, we were lucky to have the support of the host institution, CeNAT and CONARE (Consejo Nacional de Rectores). Additionally, RStudio provided two scholarships to bring one student from Belize and another one from Nicaragua. The goal of this workshop was to train researchers in Research Data Science (RDS). RDS refers to the principles and practice of Open Science and research data management and curation, the use of a range of data platforms and infrastructures, large scale analysis, statistics, visualization and modelling techniques, software development and data annotation. These are important tools for extracting useful information from data and these tools are useful in every research area.

Python. The Python section was welcomed very positively by students that were already familiar with it, but also by R and Matlab users, making this change at #dataSanJosé19 a successful experiment.

Nazareth Lopez

My experience at the CODATA - Research Data Science Summer School was wonderful. An exceptional program of lectures, great teaching methodologies and technological tools that ensure knowledge sharing. The environment created by the organizers and the professors made a full space perfect to participate, make networking, friends, partners for future projects. I enjoyed each moment talking with everybody in the room. Participating in the summer school marked a before and an after in my career as a young biotechnologist oriented to data science. I have developed a set of skills and tools really valuable, and a sense of continuous learning.

Moisés Humberto Castellón Martínez

Before attending CODATA-RDA dataSanJose19, data science was a kind of buzzword to me. The previous six months, I had been hearing about machine learning, neural networks, natural language processing and many other fascinating topics that are complex and I had no true interaction with them. Applying and being admitted for CODATA-RDA summer school Costa Rica became the milestone of the year for me and it finally happened.

I couldn't be more enthusiastic about attending a CODATA-RDA school because I had read a lot about how these schools have changed many students' lives around the world. My case would not be an exception, dataSanJose19 was outstanding in all aspects; well organized, instructors and helpers committed to a good cause and provide an exceptional experience to students from unique

this lengthy journey in becoming a data scientist, to share with teammates, friends, and other people about all what I learnt. Last but not least, I made wonderful friends and collaborators for future projects.

Pretoria January 2020

The first South African CODATA-RDA Research Data Summer School was hosted from 13 – 24 January 2020 at the University of Pretoria (UP)'s Department of Information Science. The Summer School was facilitated in collaboration with the Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa (DIRISA), South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR) and the Network of Data and Information Curation Communities (NeDICC) and Data Carpentry SA. Although the SS was hosted in Pretoria any early career researchers (M-level to postdoc) based in Africa had the opportunity to hands-on exposure to the foundational data science skills required of modern research taking our own unique context into consideration. The participants had the opportunity to use several useful tools / technologies and gained technical skills within the broader context of responsible and reproducible research practices.

The interest in the School was considerably bigger than what we had anticipated. Only a third of the applicants could be selected to participate. Although candidates were expected to cover their own sustenance and accommodation costs, 48 (forty-eight) participants – 22 of them female and representing the following countries: Botswana, Congo, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Nigeria, Sudan, Eswatini, Tanzania, Uganda, Zimbabwe and South Africa [graphics provided], were willing to go through the intensive programme. A select number of the attendees were librarians (representing Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, Tanzania, and Uganda) and who had previously completed their Masters degrees at UP as part of a Carnegie-sponsored M.IT programme. They all indicated that they are wanting to take the Summer School concept to their own countries. In doing so the training will become much more affordable to a significant larger number of Masters and PhD students in more African countries. It will immediately increase the impact of the initiative while giving the libraries the opportunity to coordinate the training. UP's Department of Information Science is currently investigating the requirements to support such a network of African Summer Schools. The diversity in focus and background of the participants led to interesting discussions but also allowed participants to see that they all shared similar concerns, had similar constraints and that they could, together, come up with solutions that were innovative and immediately helpful.

The Steering Committee believe that the participants gained the necessary exposure to practices and knowledge that will allow them to work with their data in the transparent, effective and efficient manner required by 21st century research practices. We also firmly believe that this School will have a long-term impact on the careers of our participants. From our own research there is a definite need for an event such as the Summer School in South Africa as well as the African countries north of our borders. We, the organisers, now understand the curriculum and administrative requirements considerably better and we have documented the learning gained so that future events would be even better. The next South African school is being planned for 2021 and, given the current constraints, it

Albert Buabeng

In January 2020, I was invited to participate in the CODATA-RDA Research Data Summer School at the University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa. The Summer School imparted in me a lot and exposed me to various opportunities and resources available for enhancing and conducting responsible research in this technological era. Though my time there was short, what I will always cherish most is the warm reception and the unparalleled attention given to the Participants by the Instructors. Because of them, I have gained the strength I needed to take the next step in my academic and professional life. Attending this Summer School was the best decision I could ever make.

As a researcher, I have actively been utilising the skill, knowledge and materials I acquired during the Summer School, both in my PhD research as well as other projects and collaborations I am involved in. My role as a Lecturer draws on many facets of the knowledge I have amassed during my academic work at UMaT, the exposure and materials from the CODATA Summer School, and the experiences from projects and collaborations.

Inger Fabris-Rotelli

In January 2020, for two full weeks, I had the honour of being accepted to attend the CODATA-RDA Research Data Summer School in Pretoria, hosted at the University of Pretoria. I am a Statistician/Applied Mathematician by training and daily apply much coding in my research and lecturing. The Summer School was incredibly beneficial as it provided an over view of the use of data in one's research. The summer school covers, amongst others, the ethics of data, databases, high performance computing opportunities, Git Bash and Git, providing a good setting for anyone using data in their research. The Summer School was well organised and instructors put in huge effort.

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research fields and why they applied to do the Summer School. Being from a computational background and only being involved at the end during the analysis aspect of a project, forces your mindset to look at how other fields begin the data collection. And one can always learn more and should never close opportunities for further learning experiences!

During the current COVID-19 Pandemic I have had the opportunity to work on the CHPC with a team from the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, the Medical Research Council and the University of the Witwatersrand on modelling the spread of the virus in South Africa spatially. The knowledge gained from the Summer School helped me to immediately start this research, which I would not have been able to otherwise, as the modelling is computationally intensive and not easily done without high performance computing.

The Summer School is an excellent opportunity for a researcher from any field working with data and wanting to take ownership of their analysis and data management.

Trieste September 2020

This year, the CODATA-RDA Summer School in Trieste was held virtually. While the cancellation of the physical event was disappointing, it allowed for a new opportunity - learning how to run a virtual CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science event directed to our alumni.

The objective of the event was to give an update and teaching strategies for each of the curriculum sections that were covered during our previous schools. Our ultimate goal was to make our alumni more confident in sharing their knowledge and provide them with tools when organizing local workshops to train others.

The school format consisted of preparatory materials: each of the individual topics taught with a short review, new topics or updates since their last school, and strategies for instructing in this curriculum area. The topics were: Research Data management, Open and Responsible Research, Author Carpentry, The Carpentries (Unix, Git, R, and Python), Visualisation, Machine Learning, Artificial Neural Networks, and Computational Infrastructures.

Over the period of two weeks, students were able to attend a virtual session (one hour a day, in two different sessions to accommodate different time zones) on each of the individual topics, where they had the chance to reacquaint themselves with the materials and with their colleagues, since each session facilitated group discussions among participants.

In total, we had over 100 alumni as attendees, from 30 different countries. Fourteen different instructors worked on the materials and guided the synchronous sessions, along with the help of eight wonderful assistants who facilitated discussions and assisted with technology issues. Once more, we couldn't have done it without the support of ICTP Trieste, CODATA, RDA and FAIRsFAIR, and for that we are extremely thankful.

5 Years of Summer Schools at ICTP

It is hard to believe that there have already been five editions of the Research Data Science Schools at the ICTP. In 2015, when Data Science was a relatively young field that was generally used with discipline specific context and applications, the trio of Andrew Harrison, Hugh Shanahan and Simon Hodson visited the ICTP at Trieste Campus to propose an activity on Research Data Science: a school that was both intra and inter disciplinary in nature. The school would focus on growing practical skills and know-how in a manner that is useful to any discipline in a spirit of

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The very first edition of what has become known as the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School took place in August 2016 as a joint activity between CODATA, RDA, ICTP and TWAS (the Academy of Sciences for the Developing World). This first event brought together 100 high quality researchers (78 participants, 4 tutors, 12 lecturers and 6 organisers) from over 35 different countries and from very diverse disciplines. All five schools have been equally successful and well attended also with 50% or more women participating at all levels.

In 2017, the event was expanded to three weeks, with the third week devoted to three parallel thematic workshops on Extreme Sources of Data, IoT & Big-Data Analytics and Bioinformatics. The 2018 school included a new workshop on Climate Data Sciences, while a new track on Data Stewardship was introduced as part of the regular two-week summer school. The next edition will include additional workshops in other areas such as Augmented Visualization and Smart Cities and Environments. All alumni feel part of a larger family that are transforming their world as they put into practice the skills they acquired and supporting each other. This has contributed to the successful organisation of regional versions of the schools in Brazil, Rwanda and Puerto Rico and many other locations world-wide.

The CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer Schools have quickly become an internationally recognised event for high quality training on Research Data Sciences and continues to remain true to its core foundation of cross-disciplinary research platform. After five events, the core organisation is now managed by an expanded team that include many previous participants and instructors. There are no signs of slowing down, indeed all sponsors and organisers remain committed to maintaining the high quality of the schools and associated workshops.

Clement Onime, Local Organiser, International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), Trieste, Italy

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